

Types Of Tasks Used In Organizing The Process Of Logical Knowledge And The Process Of Logical Cognition When Teaching Molecular Biology

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Abstract: A unique aspect of teaching molecular biology is the formation in students of the ability to become familiar with biological objects, understand and interpret the processes occurring in them. Understanding the learning process is the reason for the proper organization of science teaching. The use of questions is important in organizing the educational process. This article describes the organization of the cognitive process of students and the types of biological tasks used in the cognitive process.

Keywords — Cognition, perception, object, phenomenon, thinking, analysis, perception, imagination, matter, biological object, biological concept, calculation, matter, biological problem.

INTRODUCTION.

In the process of learning, a person perceives the object he is studying and the processes related to it, compares it with another object, and as a result, he gets information about the object. Collects information by perceiving the external environment, creates a cognitive process. The learning process is a complex process and consists of several stages. In the process of knowing, if some process is not carried out sufficiently, the essence of things and events cannot be understood. This in turn hinders the generation of information and causes lack of knowledge.

In the process of teaching molecular biology to students, it is necessary to organize the knowledge process correctly. Having information about the process of learning leads to the correct organization of the process of imparting knowledge, increasing the efficiency of learning.

Through cognition, a person replaces outdated theories in his mind with new ones, and as a result, by clarifying old theories, he learns new knowledge about a subject or phenomenon. In the process of learning, the studied subject or event must go through certain stages in order for it to be reflected in the human brain.

Teaching molecular biology requires paying attention to the types of information contained in the subject. Contains text, graphic, numerical, terminological and digital information on molecular biology. It is important to organize educational creative activities to familiarize students with information on the subject. When teaching natural sciences, it is necessary to take into account the uniqueness of science in the organization of educational creative activity of students. In this case, the task of the teacher is to correctly organize, control and manage the stages of the cognitive process. In teaching molecular biology, the main emphasis is on gaining knowledge of the subject and studying processes at the molecular level. This

approach requires the use of practical, applied, natural science issues in molecular biology classes. It is learning using biological problems to develop skills in the educational process that serves to develop creative abilities.

As a problem-based approach in teaching mathematics, it is used to determine the purpose and content of education from mathematical problems, to form and develop knowledge, skills, to explain a new topic, to determine the degree of mastery of the subject. , repeat, generalize and consolidate it, form creative activity in students and develop creative and logical abilities, purposefully use a system of educational questions when teaching independent thinking, the formation of a scientific worldview.

Today, the idea of a problem-based approach has become widespread due to the fact that the main task of teaching mathematics is aimed at developing students' learning skills.

Problem solving is an important form of learning activity. While solving problems, students learn the theoretical foundations of mathematics, acquire practical skills, and acquire creative and independent ways of thinking.

One way to describe them is to identify the main stages of problem solving. Because the management of students' cognitive activity is carried out on the basis of taking into account such stages. Unlike other methodological scientists, N.R. It can be seen that Gaibullaev divides it into four stages:

Stage 1. Full understanding of the state of the matter.

Step 2: Make a plan to solve the problem.

Step 3: Implement a plan to solve the problem.

Step 4. Analysis of the problem solution.

Tasks are the leading condition for organizing students' cognitive activity in the process of learning mathematics and are an effective means of student development. The tasks serve to form a system of basic knowledge, skills and abilities in

students. Therefore, in the practice of teaching mathematics, the main part of teaching time is devoted to solving problems.

It should be noted that a mathematical model is a representation in the language of mathematics of a set of events (of the same type) or objects of real existence. The main purpose of modeling is to study these objects using mathematical methods and predict future results. It is important to note that this is a method of understanding events and processes in the environment, as well as providing the ability to control these processes. The main means of applying mathematics in practice are mathematical models. One of the most promising mathematical objects in teaching mathematical modeling are geometric models.

One of the important features of mathematical models is that they can simultaneously be models of practical, physical, chemical, biological and other processes. These models will then capture the important components and connections of the phenomena being studied. Therefore, the analysis of such models determines the possibilities for studying and researching this phenomenon. We should not forget that one mathematical model can correspond to different real phenomena.

Solving problems and exercises in molecular biology serves to enhance student learning by creating cognitive activity. Working on a problem, the student will have an opportunity to deeply study the processes of metabolism and energy in biological systems, the connections between them, current events, logical thinking of students and acceleration of educational creative activity. By applying theoretical knowledge acquired in a subject in various processes, he transforms the acquired knowledge into skills and competencies. To work on problems, you need to become familiar with their types.

The problems are divided into four categories depending on the content of the given condition: word problems, experiential problems, graphic problems and research problems. According to the content, tasks of each type are divided into tasks representing quantity and tasks representing quality. The tasks are divided into easy and difficult ones, requiring the development of skills and creativity.

If a given problem condition consists of text, such problems are called word problems. In word problems, the data is in the form of text and requires computational processing of the problem.

The practice problems are based on the order in which the laboratory exercises are performed. It will be aimed at developing the ability to quantitatively and qualitatively connect the actions performed during the experiment. Working on tasks based on experience is based on the following: first, working on a given task requires memorization and the ability to carry out experiments. Secondly, mathematical calculations are carried out in order to find connections between the

experimental stages or determine the value according to the conditions of the problem and find the answer to the problem.

Graphical tasks are tasks that require a graphical solution. Graphics issues The solution is to analyze the graph or calculation schedule. Graphics tasks can be divided into two types. The state of tasks of the first type is presented graphically. To find the answer to a problem, it is analyzed and actions are performed according to the conditions of the problem. The condition of the second type of task consists of text and numbers. To find the answer to a problem, the conditions of the problem are fulfilled and the answer is expressed graphically.

In research problems, numerical values or concepts are not sufficiently given due to the nature of the problem. By finding missing concepts or meanings from specific sources, the condition of the problem is satisfied and the answer is found.

Qualification questions—to find the answer does not require mathematical calculations. According to the conditions of the problem, it is necessary to explain the ongoing process and event, select the necessary conditions for the occurrence of the event. Numbers on these issues are not provided.

Calculation problems -problems for which the answer is found by calculating the answer in accordance with the conditions of the problem. To find the answer to calculation questions, the problem is first analyzed qualitatively. Based on the results of the analysis, options, methods for solving problems, and arithmetic or algebraic operations are determined.

Our research has shown that situations that arise when solving non-standard problems lead to the formation of the following effective skills in students: the ability to apply acquired knowledge in new situations that are not similar to those previously considered; the ability to independently work with educational and scientific literature; ability to organize your work; the ability to transfer general methods for solving problems related to one area to other areas; the ability to avoid rash actions; the ability to look for solutions to problems in different directions; the ability to see the next step in the decision process when choosing a method to solve a problem; the ability to analyze partially completed work simultaneously, retrospectively; such as the ability to continuously and systematically monitor one's problem-solving behavior.

We would like to note that solving non-standard problems and, of course, critically analyzing the process of returning to it after solving a problem very effectively contributes to the formation of a creative method in students. activities and development of creative abilities. A.N. According to Leontiev, a high level of intellectual development of students is unnoticeable when returning to a solved problem (discussion) in order to understand the solution method.

The developmental function of non-standard tasks is extremely important; such tasks are aimed at developing the

logical thinking of students, the formation of scientific and theoretical thinking in them, and the effective mastery of methods of mental activity by students. In the scientific and methodological literature, two types of developmental functions of tasks are distinguished. These are general and special functions.

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